

Scoring Instructional Utterances in Guitar Lessons using Semantic Labels and LLM

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Abstract. This study examines the utility of semantically grounded labels in private music instruction, focusing on how they capture instructional intent and identify important teaching utterances. Our prior work introduced a framework for semantic analysis of classical guitar lessons, annotating teacher utterances with six Instructional Content Labels (ICL): Giving Subjective Information, Giving Objective Information, Asking Question, Giving Feedback, Giving Practice, and Giving Advice. In this study, we extend this framework by developing an ICL-weighted scoring method that combines utterance length with semantic weights to highlight instructionally significant discourse. We also reinterpret ICL categories for real-time spoken instruction, assigning higher weights to actionable guidance. To validate this approach, we compared our scoring outputs against rankings generated by multiple large language models—GPT-4.5, GPT-4o, and Claude Opus 4—across 24 classical guitar lessons. All models showed significantly stronger alignment with ICL-weighted scores than length-only baselines. Claude Opus 4 achieved near-perfect correlation ($\rho = 0.993$), while GPT-4.5 also demonstrated strong alignment ($\rho = 0.902$). These findings suggest that ICL-weighted scoring can capture instructional priorities and that general-purpose LLMs may approximate domain-specific judgments. The framework may provide a foundation for automated instructional analysis in music education.

Keywords: Instructional content · Guitar lessons · Semantic scoring · Large language models.

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1 Introduction

Lessons in instrumental music involve a unique form of interactive communication between teachers and students. This communication occurs through playing sounds, verbal feedback and dialogue, and singing (see Fig. 1). Such lessons often involve repeated, step-by-step instruction on the same piece of music over multiple sessions. While students can record each lesson using audio or video, reviewing this material is often too time-consuming to be practical. This makes it difficult to reflect on or fully understand previous instruction. Therefore, developing an approach that enables the structured review of past lessons remains a key challenge.

To address this issue, we previously developed a framework for the semantic analysis and annotation of teacher utterances in one-to-one classical guitar lessons. The aim was to clarify the instructional intentions embedded in verbal feedback across multiple sessions [8,9]. In this framework, teacher utterances were categorized from conceptual and instructional perspectives using six semantic labels, revealing structural patterns within lesson content. While these studies provided valuable insights into the semantic characteristics of music instruction, they remained theoretical and did not contribute directly to practical lessons. Effective methods for supporting reflection, exploration, and reuse of lesson content by teachers and students are still lacking.

This study aims to reinterpret Instructional Content Labels (ICL), originally designed for annotation, as functional indicators of instructional intent. We introduced an ICL-weighted scoring method to prioritize instructional utterances in private guitar lessons and evaluate its consistency using both human-annotated and machine-generated rankings. As a result, we found that the ICL-weighted scores were consistent with the pedagogical intuitions reflected in the language models' rankings, with GPT-4.5 and Claude Opus 4 showing strong correlations. Claude, in particular, achieved near-perfect agreement across 24 lessons, suggesting that general-purpose LLMs can reliably approximate domain-specific instructional judgments.

The contribution of this study is as follows:

- We reinterpret manually annotated semantic labels (ICL) in music lessons as functional indicators of instructional intent.
- We evaluate the generalizability of ICL using large language models, revealing their potential for automated instructional analysis.

We position this study as a first step toward automated, pedagogically aware analysis of instructional discourse in music education. While our current focus is on verbal instruction, future work could integrate multimodal elements—such as gestures, posture, and acoustic environment.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 gives an overview of earlier research on instructional aspects. Section 3 presents our dataset of multiple classical guitar lessons and investigates the usefulness of ICL. Section 4 presents the proposed ICL-weighted scoring method and evaluates its validity by comparing

Fig. 1. Audio information in classical guitar lessons.

it to large language model outputs. It also discusses the results. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper and outlines directions for future research.

2 Related Work

To understand how teachers convey instructional intent, it is essential to consider teacher–student interaction, the structure of pedagogical discourse, and emerging applications of language models in education. This section reviews these foundational areas.

2.1 Teacher–Student Interaction in Music Lessons

Research on one-to-one music instruction has revealed complex dynamics of pedagogical communication. Daniel et al. [3] demonstrated that individual lessons tend to be teacher-dominated, limiting student-initiated interaction. Conversely, Yamamoto et al. [19] observed that in professional-level instruction, musical expression emerges through collaborative teacher-student exchanges. Hasumi et al. [5] further illustrated how teachers guide collaborative phrase development in jazz improvisation contexts.

However, most studies focus on single-session interactions. In practice, instrumental instruction unfolds across multiple sessions, with teachers providing iterative guidance on the same repertoire. This cumulative dimension of teaching and learning remains underexplored.

The shift to online instruction during the COVID-19 pandemic has further underscored the importance of verbal communication. Hrabluk [6] found that teachers view online lessons as pedagogically effective despite technological constraints, highlighting the central role of spoken instruction.

Furthermore, recent meta-synthesis research has identified four crucial aspects for effective musical learning: framing of teaching, taking learners’ perspectives, scaffolding strategies, and representation of sounding music [4]. These findings provide a broader context for understanding how verbal instruction contributes to overall pedagogical effectiveness.

2.2 Semantic Annotation in Instructional Contexts

Educational discourse analysis has employed various frameworks to categorize instructional communication. Traditional approaches include Zhukov’s [21] three-category system (modeling, instruction, feedback) and Simones et al.’s [16] analysis of gesture use across student proficiency levels.

Classroom discourse research has extensively studied Initiation-Response-Evaluation (IRE) and Initiation-Response-Feedback (IRF) patterns [17], which often dominate traditional educational settings. Understanding these established patterns provides crucial context for interpreting the pedagogical significance of different utterance types in specialized instructional contexts like music lessons.

CROCUS (CRitique dOCumentS) [15, 14, 11] is a collection of instructional feedback on instrumental performance in the form of written critiques. Currently, it covers three instruments—oboe, piano, and classical guitar—with a total of 635 critiques provided by 49 teachers for 213 performance recordings⁵. To validate its utility, the researchers developed a set of domain-specific semantic tags to annotate these critiques, demonstrating high relevance and inter-rater reliability. In the oboe dataset, inter-rater agreement between two annotators reached Cohen’s $\kappa = 0.96$. Our ICL framework draws directly on CROCUS, while adapting its methodology to the context of real-time spoken instruction to address the challenges of annotating spontaneous pedagogical discourse.

2.3 Large Language Models in Educational Discourse

The emergence of large language models has created new opportunities for automated educational analysis. There are many types of applications such as enhancing the quality of teaching plans [7], writing feedback generation [20] and students’ assignments [2].

In instructional discourse analysis, Jensen et al. [10] developed systems for extracting pedagogically salient teacher utterances, while Ma et al. [13] applied generative models to real-time learner monitoring. Recent studies have demonstrated that LLMs can achieve human-level performance in analyzing classroom dialogue, particularly in identifying discourse patterns and providing automated feedback [18, 12]. Complementary research has applied NLP-based semantic similarity analysis to classroom discourse [1], showing that automated methods can capture subtle aspects of teacher–student interaction quality.

Our study extends this trajectory by examining whether LLMs can consistently identify pedagogical importance in structured lesson data, using human-derived semantic annotations as validation criteria.

3 Lesson Data and Interpretation of Instructional Labels

This section presents the dataset of classical guitar lessons developed in previous work and outlines the semantic labeling scheme applied to teacher utterances.

⁵ <https://masaki-cb.github.io/crocus/>

We then examine the semantic usefulness of these labels and reinterpret them for the real-time context of spoken instruction.

3.1 Overview of the Lesson Dataset

Our dataset consists of 24 private classical guitar lessons targeting seven pieces, with at least two sessions dedicated to each piece. The lessons were performed by three teacher-student pairs (two instructors and three students in total), resulting in approximately 8.5 hours of recorded instruction in total. Each lesson is indexed by a song ID (e.g., LS1) and a session number (e.g., LS1-1 for the first session of song LS1). The dataset is available on GitHub⁶, excluding raw audio for privacy reasons.

This dataset was previously annotated with semantic labels for teacher utterances in our previous study [9]. In this study, we build upon that framework to explore the practical utility and interpretation of these labels.

3.2 Instructional Content Label (ICL)

The Instructional Content Label (ICL) refers to the semantic labels mentioned above. It categorizes semantic elements, such as the teacher’s intended message, and is based on textual critique research (CROCUS). We adjusted our definitions for the real-time spoken context of music lessons because they often feature overlapping concepts and incomplete phrasing. The ICL consist of the following labels:

- Giving Subjective Information (GSI): teacher providing general and/or specific conceptual information based on teacher’s subjectivity.
- Giving Objective Information (GOI): teacher providing general and/or specific conceptual information based on objectively referable events or concepts.
- Asking Question (AQ): enquiring.
- Giving Feedback (GF): teacher evaluation of a student’s applied and/or conceptual knowledge.
- Giving Practice (GP): providing suggestions of ways to practice a particular passage or discussing a practicing schedule.
- Giving Advice (GA): giving a specific opinion or recommendation without demonstration or modelling to guide the student’s action towards the achievement of certain specific musical aims.

To ensure annotation reliability, two researchers independently labeled a subset of the lesson data, achieving 94.5% inter-annotator agreement for ICL assignments. This high agreement rate demonstrates the consistency and applicability of the ICL framework to real-time spoken instruction, despite the inherent challenges of annotating spontaneous speech compared to written critiques.

⁶ <https://github.com/guitar-san/guitar-lesson-data>

Fig. 2. Histogram of ICL in best 10% and worst 10% of critique documents.

3.3 ICL Patterns in Useful Instructional Feedback

Matsubara et al. [14] showed that certain ICL labels appear more frequently in critiques of oboe performances within the CROCUS dataset when rated as highly useful. In particular, tags such as GA and GP were strongly associated with higher perceived usefulness.

We analyzed the distribution of ICL in the top and bottom 10% of usefulness scores in classical guitar critiques (N=252), based on both third-party and performer evaluations. The results are shown in Figure 2(a). As was the case with the oboe, the top 10% had more labels (GOI, GF, GP, and GA) than the bottom 10% (more than twice as many). This suggests that usefulness scores tend to increase with the amount of labeled information in critique texts.

Figure 2(b) shows the results of the performers' analysis of usefulness scores. Compared to the crowdsourcing results, the number of labels tended to decrease overall. This suggests that third parties, such as crowdsourcers, are more strongly influenced by the amount of information in the critique text. Conversely, this implies that, for the performers, having more information alone is insufficient.

3.4 Reinterpreting ICL Based on Annotator Differences

While our analysis using CROCUS (Section 3.3) revealed a correlation between certain ICL labels and higher usefulness ratings, similar patterns were not observed in our lesson dataset. This discrepancy can be attributed to differences in the nature of the data (spoken, real-time instruction vs. written critique) and in the profiles of the annotators.

The ICL in CROCUS were annotated by two musicians (Group A) who had general musical experience, but no background in classical guitar. In contrast, the lesson data in this study were annotated by two researchers (Group B). One of these researchers is a professional classical guitarist and teacher.

When comparing the annotated labels between Group A and Group B, we observed inconsistencies in the application of specific labels. For example, utterances labelled as GOI (objective information) by Group A were often labelled

as GF (feedback) by Group B, particularly when the utterance was evaluative in tone. Similarly, the distinction between GA (advice) and GP (practice) was interpreted differently: Group A tended to classify general instructional suggestions as GP, whereas Group B reserved GP for concrete, repeatable actions and labelled broader guidance as GA.

These findings suggest that real-time instruction’s usefulness depends more on directive content than on information quantity. As such, we reinterpreted the label distribution by prioritising the functional categories GF and GP, which reflect direct pedagogical interventions. In addition, we remapped ambiguous GOI utterances to GF and GA utterances to GP, in order to better align with the communicative intent observed in the lesson context.

4 Semantic Scoring and Evaluation

Building on the label interpretation adjustments presented in Section 3.4, we have developed a method for assigning importance score to each utterance.

4.1 Instructional Importance Scoring Method

To identify pedagogically salient utterances across the 24 classical guitar lessons⁶, we developed a scoring method that incorporates both utterance length and semantic label relevance. Since the number of utterances varied widely between lessons (total: 1669 teacher utterances), we designed a weighted importance score that reflects both the quantity and instructional value of each utterance.

Let L denote the character count of a given utterance segment and tL the total character count of all utterances in the same lesson (e.g. LS1-1). The relative length of the utterance is given by $\frac{L}{tL} \times 100$, representing its proportion of the lesson’s total verbal content. Each utterance is also annotated with one Instructional Content Label (ICL), for which we assign a semantic weight w : GF=5, GP=4, GA=3, GOI=2, GSI=1, AQ=0.

These weights were determined based on the reinterpretation of ICL categories discussed in Section 3.4. In that analysis, many utterances initially labeled as GOI were functionally closer to GF utterances, and utterances labeled as GA often aligned with GP. As a result, GF emerges as the most frequent and pedagogically central category, with GP occupying a nearly equivalent level of importance. We therefore assign the highest weights to GF (=5) and GP (=4), followed by GA (=3) and GOI (=2), which remain relevant but less directive. Finally, GSI (=1) and AQ (=0) are weighted lowest, as they primarily provide impressions or elicit responses rather than direct instruction.

The final importance score is calculated as:

$$importance = \left(\frac{L}{tL} \times 100 \right) \times w$$

This score assigns greater importance to utterances that are both relatively long and semantically more instructive.

4.2 Comparison with Length-only Baseline

We first investigated the effectiveness of our instructional importance scoring by comparing it with a length-only baseline. Specifically, we analyzed:

- **ICL-weighted Score (*importance*)**: Uses both length and label weight
- **Length-only Score**: Ignores semantic labels

We applied each method to a lesson (LS1-3), which was selected at random. For each method, we extracted the top 5 utterances by importance score and analyzed their distribution, content, and perceived teaching usefulness.

To investigate the effect of semantic weighting on identifying pedagogically significant utterances, we compared the top five utterances from lesson LS1-3 selected using two scoring methods. Table 1 presents the utterances, their instructional labels, text length, and computed importance score. All utterances were translated from Japanese to English for clarity.

While both methods identified the same utterance as most important—a long advisory statement on performance pacing—the remaining selections diverged significantly. The ICL-weighted method surfaced utterances that included GP and GF, such as:

- “Try using the whole arm. That excessive motion isn’t necessary.” (GF)
- “The ring finger, it’s tricky unless you align it correctly.” (GP)

These utterances, though shorter, received higher importance score due to their pedagogical function. In contrast, some of the selected utterances under the Length-based setting lacked clear directive or corrective intent. such as:

- “That D note just now was really nice” (GSI)

To further validate our semantic scoring scheme, we calculated Spearman’s ρ between the ICL-weighted and length-based rankings for each lesson, using the `rank()` method with ‘average’ tie-breaking. The average correlation across all lessons was $\rho = 0.868$, indicating partial agreement but also highlighting the distinct contribution of semantic weighting. Especially, the presence of GP and GF labels among the top-ranked results suggests that combining utterance length with semantic role may lead to more pedagogically meaningful prioritization.

4.3 LLM-Based Usefulness Analysis

To test whether LLMs are capable of recognizing utterances that are teaching-focused in guitar instruction, we compared their output with two benchmarks: our proposed instructional importance score and a simple baseline based solely on utterance length.

Table 1. Top-5 Utterances for Lesson LS1-3 under Each Scoring Method (English Translation)

Rank	Method	Utterance (translated excerpt)	ICL	Length	Importance
1	ICL-weighted	You played at a fairly fast tempo like before, so from now on, try to listen to each note and shape the musical story — no need to rush; let’s aim for a more careful performance.	GA	147	19.36
2	ICL-weighted	Also, some notes are getting too soft, so feel free to bring each one out more clearly. I get it, but I want to fix that.	GF	76	15.01
3	ICL-weighted	It feels like you’re focusing only on the fingers — try using the whole arm. That excessive motion isn’t necessary.	GF	65	12.84
4	ICL-weighted	Yes, exactly — especially the ring finger, it’s tricky unless you align it correctly.	GP	64	10.54
5	ICL-weighted	If you could adjust it a little more... it’s not just about playing well, it’s about conveying the music to the audience.	GA	80	10.54
1	Length-based	You played at a fairly fast tempo like before, so from now on, try to listen to each note and shape the musical story — no need to rush; let’s aim for a more careful performance.	GA	147	19.36
2	Length-based	I think it’s okay to let the rhythm breathe a bit — even if the overall tempo is the same, you can add expression internally.	GSI	125	8.23
3	Length-based	If you could adjust it a little more... it’s not just about playing well, it’s about conveying the music to the audience.	GA	80	10.54
4	Length-based	Also, some notes are getting too soft, so feel free to bring each one out more clearly. I get it, but I want to fix that.	GF	76	15.01
5	Length-based	That D note just now was really nice — much better than before.	GSI	76	5.00

Table 2. Spearman’s ρ : LLM agreement with ICL-weighted and length-based ranks (lesson-level mean)

Model	vs. Importance Score	vs. Length Score
GPT-4.5	0.902	0.693
GPT-4o	0.691	0.517
Claude Opus 4	0.993	0.856

Table 3. Top-N overlap between LLM-selected utterances and ICL-weighted scores (lesson-level mean)

Model	Top-5 Overlap	Top-5 Rate (%)	Top-10 Overlap	Top-10 Rate (%)
GPT-4.5	3.63	72.5	7.38	73.8
GPT-4o	2.13	42.5	5.21	52.1
Claude Opus 4	4.54	90.8	9.29	92.9

Method: Prompting and Models We used two OpenAI models—GPT-4.5 and GPT-4o—and Claude Opus 4 by Anthropic as representative LLMs. Each model received all teacher utterances from 24 classical guitar lessons. Inputs were structured as: (1) utterance ID, (2) lesson ID, (3) ICL, and (4) utterance text. The models were instructed to rank the utterances in each lesson by instructional importance. The full prompts are available on GitHub⁷.

Results: Agreement with Semantic vs. Length Scores We computed Spearman’s rank correlation coefficients (ρ) between the LLM-assigned rankings and two human-defined rankings—the proposed instructional importance and a length-only baseline.

As shown in Table 2, all LLMs correlated more strongly with the instructional importance score than with length alone. Notably, Claude Opus 4 achieved the highest correlation, indicating a strong ability to approximate our ICL-weighted instructional focus. This suggests that LLMs respond not just to surface-level textual features but also to the semantic content reflected by ICL.

In addition, statistical analysis across 24 lessons revealed that all models showed significantly stronger alignment with ICL-weighted importance score compared to length-only baselines. The effect sizes were substantial (Cohen’s $d > 1.0$ for all models), indicating not only statistical significance but also practical importance of the semantic weighting approach.

Results: Top-N Utterance Overlap We computed the Top-5 and Top-10 utterance overlap between the ICL-weighted scores and the LLM-generated rankings for each lesson, and then averaged both the overlap counts and percentages across all 24 lessons (Tab. 3).

Claude also achieved the highest overlap across both Top-5 and Top-10 levels, further confirming its alignment with the ICL-weighted importance framework.

⁷ <https://github.com/guitar-san/guitar-lesson-data/tree/main/prompts>

These results reinforce the robustness our scoring and suggest that large language models can generalize instructional relevance effectively across multiple architectures.

4.4 Discussion

The results confirm that semantic label weighting provides a more meaningful prioritization of instructional utterances than surface-level features (length). Utterances marked with high-weighted labels such as GF and GP consistently appeared in the top ranks, reinforcing the educational relevance of ICL. Claude Opus 4, in particular, was able to replicate these rankings with near-perfect accuracy. This may be attributed to differences in instruction tuning and semantic sensitivity, which warrant further investigation.

Importantly, the notion of “importance” varies with learner profiles and instructional goals. For beginning students acquiring technique, GP-weighted utterances (e.g., “Press the string while harnessing arm weight.”) provide essential procedural guidance. Intermediate students refining performance may benefit more from GF-weighted feedback (e.g., “Some notes are too soft—bring them out more clearly.”). Advanced students exploring interpretation might value GSI/GOI utterances that discuss musical context. Despite this variability, the strong alignment between LLM rankings and ICL-weighted scores across models supports the generality and robustness of the proposed framework.

Taken together, these findings suggest that ICL are effective not only as an annotation scheme. They also provide a solid foundation for automating instructional reflection. This positions our scoring method as a practical entry point for scalable, semantically informed analysis in music pedagogy and beyond.

5 Conclusion

This study proposed a method for identifying teaching-focused utterances in private music lessons by combining utterance length with semantic labels (ICL). The resulting weighted importance score reflected instructional priorities more accurately than a length-only baseline.

To validate the framework, we compared it against rankings generated by large language models. All tested models—GPT-4.5, GPT-4o, and Claude Opus 4 showed significantly stronger alignment with the ICL-weighted scores than with the length-only baseline. Among all models, Claude demonstrated the strongest alignment, indicating that the semantic cues captured by ICL generalize well across model architectures.

These results affirm the utility of ICL as a scaffold for instructional prioritization, and suggest that LLMs can serve as practical proxies for human annotators in identifying salient teaching moments. The proposed framework thus holds promise for scalable applications in lesson reflection, summary, and teaching support.

However, several limitations should be acknowledged: (1) the dataset is limited to classical guitar lessons in Japanese, potentially limiting generalizability; (2) the ICL weights were assigned based on expert judgment rather than empirical validation; (3) evaluation with actual teachers and students is needed to assess practical utility.

Future work will incorporate human evaluations to assess the perceived instructional value of utterances. We also plan to explore automatic ICL assignment using fine-tuned LLMs and extend the scoring framework to include multimodal lesson data such as gesture and audio. Finally, we aim to apply the approach to instructional domains beyond music education.

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